

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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THE SEMANTICS OF WHITE AND BLACK COLOR SYMBOLS (BASED ON NAKHCHIVAN FOLKLORE TEXTS)

Colors are considered fundamental indicators of nature and serve as symbols that emphasize the characteristics of objects. For modern people, changing the color of objects, as well as elements belonging to nature when necessary, is not surprising at all. But no matter how strong this change is, nature expresses its reaction in different ways in response to the change in color. Likewise, a change in color is not a change in the feature of an object. Nevertheless, color occupies an important position in the existence and formation of the natural feature of the thing. Colors are also indicators of consciousness. Colors live in consciousness. It moves from consciousness to objects. And the best place for its manifestation is in the field of oral literature - folklore. The article examines the reflection of colors, which are among the means of manifestation of consciousness, in folklore, and their role and significance in revealing the essence of folklore examples.

Keywords: colors, white color, black color, symbolism of colors, examples of folklore, ethnic thought

Introduction: For ancient people, colors constituted a highly significant system of signs. Sources indicate that each color had its own unique characteristics for them, and these characteristics carried deep meanings. This is also confirmed by folklore and ethnographic memory that has survived to this day. It is also undeniable that colors, which carry a variety of symbols in modern times, had a system of meanings that contradicted them in ancient times. Today we can observe them within the scope of folklore examples. It is also observed that the same color has a different character at different times. Folklore and ethnography clearly indicate that black, associated with mourning and grief in modern times, was firmly established in the last century and continues in our era as a color predominantly used in mourning ceremonies. However, it is undeniable that black has a positive meaning and a character that radiates optimism. It is for this reason that in our modern day, black is already returning to its former semantic capacity – the totality of a positive nature. Today, in the opening ceremonies of many catering establishments, as well as on birthdays, accessories of black color are used, based on the desire of the person himself. Black is frequently used in written literary works to reveal characters' traits and to describe and present events. In general, the world of colors is a system of signs that is as mysterious as it is capable of conveying messages from deep layers. In different nations of the world, the symbolism of colors is derived from the ancient beliefs of that particular nation. A color that expresses a certain meaning in one nation may have completely opposite meanings in another.

“In some cases, colors become symbols that define the content of objects and events, as well as the characteristics and emotions of people. For example, while all over the world white is considered the color of light, success, happiness, or even God, this is not the case with other colors. For instance, while in many nations, yellow is known as a symbol of activity,

compassion, and kindness; red represents gathering and unity; and blue (or sky blue) signifies anger, rage, excitement, and protest - among most Turkic peoples, including Azerbaijani Turks, yellow symbolizes drought, famine, malice, and envy; red is associated with conflict, war, and madness (as reflected in the proverb “The madman loves red”); green represents abundance and prosperity; and blue signifies joy, happiness, and good news.” (Abdulla / Azerbaijan ethnography: 2007, 423).

Main part: In Azerbaijani folklore and ethnography, the semantics of colors are closely connected to the ancient ethnic thinking of this people. Just like numbers, colors are also closely related to the unique philosophical thinking of the Azerbaijani Turks. The object from which this thought also originates are such moments as the ancient culture of the people, its history, the ceremonial factor that expresses in itself the interaction with nature. Many scientists and researchers conducted research on the semantic explanation of colors in the folklore world of the Azerbaijani Turks at different times, presented the results in the form of books and articles. The late folklorist Bahlul Abdulla also discussed the diversity in the presentation of colors in the folklore and ethnography of the Azerbaijani Turks. It should be noted that we can also observe this diversity in many cases in the regions of Azerbaijan. We observe different manifestations of colors in the examples of oral culture of Nakhchivan and its regions, where folklore and ethnographic ideas are preserved in each period of conservatism. In general, it should be noted that in the presentation of colors within folklore examples, we also find many contrasting points, that is, the issue of contrasting colors. For example, it is known and clear that it is black that acts in a position contrasting with white. However, in the folklore and ethnographic phenomena of some territories, the contrasting position with white, that is, the opposite color, is red.

In general, white color is the color in which many symbolic elements are concentrated in oral culture. “White is the color of purity and righteousness, the most universal expression of a clean heart. Unlike black, it has a special place in the color system, expressing the universal and associated with the Absolute. It was previously perceived as the color of sacrificed creatures. White is the sixth chakra in religious and yoga traditions... In Tibetan tradition, white is considered the color of Mount Meru, located at the center of the world, and is considered a symbol of light and freshness...” (Encyclopedia. Symbols, Signs, Emblems. Astrel: 2004, 76). In most examples of the genres of all types of folklore, the expression of white color stemming from sacred thinking is evident. Whether in the early genres or in larger texts such as tales, legends, and epics, the sacred aspects of the initial belief system related to the color white can be observed. This is also the case in folklore samples collected from Nakhchivan. In these examples, we see the presentation of the color white in a positive sense, that is, the concept designated by the color white is a general sign of the positive direction of the events occurring in the text. Thus, the hero's encounter with a person on a white horse in times of distress or difficulty symbolizes that they will achieve success in the subsequent course of events. When the hero encounters a concept associated with the color white (such as a road, horse, cloth, socks, etc.) during long and arduous trials and challenges, it signals their future success. In the fairy tale “Golden Rooster” (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore: 2010, 223), the hero, who embarks on a journey to obtain the rooster held by twelve giants, is advised that a **white horse** will aid him. “*The black horse will throw you onto the white horse. The white horse will take you to the place where the golden rooster is. You will extend the rope and take the golden rooster, but you will not return until you reach here*” (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore: 2010, 223).

In the examples of the lyrical genre, such as bayati, there is information about the sacredness of the color white. In these bayatis, the concepts defined by the color white convey a message about the lyrical hero's successful future. In expressions such as white scarf, white paper, white socks, etc., the association of these items with the color white enhances their sacredness. Because in these examples, the color white is presented as a symbol of purity, success, and happiness.

Kağızın ağa dönər,
(The paper turns white),

Yazısı ağa dönər.
(Its writing turns white).

Sən qapıdan girəndə
(When you enter through the door),

Ürəyim dağa dönər
(My heart turns into a mountain). (The road to Ordubad. Folklore collection. Nakhchivan: 2005, 62).

Here, the paper is synonymous with the concept of the written fate about a person's future, written by God, which is referred to as “forehead writing”. The meaning of “writing whitens the written forehead, expands and opens due to whiteness” clarifies the role of ağ (white)

in the first line. The white in the second line is equivalent to the concepts of “white day” and “white luck”. When the lyrical hero is reunited with their love, the success and happiness that will follow are symbolized by the color white.

The color white also plays a key role in overcoming the pain of separation, longing, and exile. The color white also plays a key role in overcoming the pain of separation, longing, and exile.

Corabın ağına bax,
(Look at the white of the sock),
Dəstələ, bağına bax.
(Tie it up, look at its bundle).
Mən yadına düşəndə
(When you remember me),
Naxçıvan dağına bax

(Look at the Nakhchivan mountain) (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Nakhchivan folklore: 1994, 278).

The Russian researcher A.M.Petrov writes that the color white is the most widely spread symbol in the color symbolism of Russian and world culture. In his view, white usually carries a positive ethical and aesthetic value. “*In the Christian world, this color is a symbol of purity and holiness. White (and sometimes light colors) is recognized as the attribute of saints in religious poetry. The hero Yegor is depicted on a white horse in his battle with the snake while rescuing Princess Elizabeth*” (Petrov, 2011: 26).

The image of the old man with white hair and a white beard is also an equivalent of the wise old man archetype in fairy tales as well as epic texts. The whiteness of the hair and beard here indicates that the exemplary hero presented is a worldly person who lived a long life. And with the color white, these qualities are both generalized and sacralized: *Başına döndüyüm, ata,*
(My dear father, whom I cherish),
Bir qız məni dərdə salıb.
(A girl has cast me into sorrow).
Ağ saqqalın nura batıb,
(Your white beard is bathed in light),
Bir qız məni dərdə salıb
(A girl has cast me into sorrow). (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Nakhchivan folklore: 1994, 336). The contrast between “white beard” and “light” in epic and fairy tale texts indicates that the addressed figure or hero is both wise and illuminated by divine power.

The character of White Giant in fairy tales and mythological texts collected from Nakhchivan stands out as a powerful and strong figure, as well as a being with positive traits and a benevolent spirit. The White Giant usually does not harm those around him; even if he does cause harm, he possesses the ability to reform himself. In ancient Turkic thought, a space painted white was considered a means of bringing a bright day and a happy future to a person. Similarly, in the “Book of Dede Korkut” epic, the motif of inviting someone with a son to a white tent signifies the sacred aspect of the color white in this context. Traces of that thought are clearly visible in the examples of bayati collected from Nakhchivan:

Əlində gül tutan yar!
(The lover holding a flower in hand!)
Ağ otaxda yatan yar!

(The lover sleeping in a white room)!

Sevdin, sevdin, tərək etdin,

(You loved, you loved, and then abandoned),

Allahdan bir utan yar!

(May you feel ashamed before God)! (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. II: 2011, 221).

It is well known that blessings and curses, as examples of early genres, reflect the belief in the magical power of words. And as elements of ethnic thought pass through the filter of time, they first become preserved in these examples. Therefore, it is possible to find instances in blessings and curses that reflect the sacredness of the color white. In these examples, the concept defined by white represents success and a prosperous future.

May you never see white days. (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. III: 2012, 143);

May you never find white bread. (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. III: 2012, 142);

May you reach white days. (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. III: 2012, 140);

May you have bright days and white bread. (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. III: 2012, 38).

Regarding the color white, the late folklorist Bahlul Abdulla provided a comprehensive and clear explanation in his article “The semantic symbolism of white color” in the Book of Dede Korkut. The scientist's symbolism of the color white in the work in question also helps to clarify the deep world of symbols related to the color white in ancient Turkic thought. In the article, the scholar rightfully considers white to be the most sacred and supreme of all revered colors and writes about it as follows: “The sacred color white in creation myths also signifies God, lineage, and ancestral origins, or serves as an identifying and distinguishing feature associated with these concepts. The Sakha people consider the sacred white color to be the symbol of Urung-Ayyiq Toyon (the White Creator), the deity who created the entire world and everything within it. As is well known, the hero of the Sakha creation epic “Er Sogotoh” is also called Agoglan (white boy). Because, according to belief, he is the first human being created by the supreme God – the White Creator” (The world of Dede Korkut: 2004, 212). White is not only the color of holiness and sanctity, but also the color of life itself. As mentioned, the deep symbolism of white, which radiates sacredness, is even more actively observed in folklore examples. The expression “white days” is the best example to describe the happiest periods of a person's life. In Nakhchivan folklore examples, the color white carries deep symbolism, expressing happiness and a prosperous life. The examples emphasize the idea of a prosperous life through the color white.

Black color - Primarily, the symbolism of black, which has been formed as the color of mourning and grief, becomes clearer in ancient mythological thoughts depending on the context in which it is used. In other

words, while black predominantly maintains its character as the color of mourning today, its original meanings are emphasized differently within folklore examples, reflecting a variety of symbolic interpretations. Primarily, religious attributes associated with the color black, and its function as a defining element in these attributes, prevent the color from losing its symbolic meaning in modern times. Nevertheless, the color black takes on different meanings, which can be observed from early genre examples to epic texts. Even gradually, it is being reflected in written literature and it is being denied that the color black represents mourning and mourning in its entirety. In this regard, our immortal poet Rasul Rza says in a poem:

They say black is the color of mourning,

- No, it's a lie! Lift your eyelashes, and convince me with your eyes (...).

As the poet said, black is the color of the eyes, which are the mirror of the heart. Black was used in ancient Turks to mean big, head, first. According to ethnographic data collected from Nakhchivan, it is known that in different periods, elderly women who wore the kelaghayi headscarf - those who had lived long lives and possessed significant life experience - would use black-colored kelaghayis. Women based their choice of kelaghayi colors not on their age but on their life experiences. Middle-aged women wore kelaghayis in a chickpea color, young women and brides chose white, while girls wore red kelaghayis. This ethnographic data clearly shows that black symbolizes primacy, wisdom, and leadership. However, in global mythological thought, black also represents death, fog, and chaos. In Christian mythology, black was considered a symbol of cruelty. This symbolism was rooted in dark forces and witchcraft. In Indo-Aryan myths, horse figures representing the two worlds were depicted in white and black colors. In ancient Tibetan myths, information about a ritual says that in the position of the victim, they painted the face and body of the chosen person in two colors, white and black. Here, the color black symbolized the first, the beginning, and the initial stage of all processes. In one of the myths about Prophet Noah, it is also said that he first sent out a black raven and only later released white doves into nature. Since black is considered the beginning of everything, he first sent the black bird into the air.

In Nakhchivan folklore materials, we sometimes observe that black color is evil spirit. This is observed in the primary genres – faith and trials:

They do not let a black cat into the house, as it is believed to bring fear (Examples of Sharur folklore. I book: 2016, 17).

The black cat is perceived as a symbol of misfortune in folk thought. Even in popular lexicon, there is a saying derived from this belief: when someone faces difficulties, people say: perhaps a black cat crossed your path when you left home in the morning. This approach is not about the color black. The fact that a black cat is a symbol of bad luck is about the cat itself. According to folk beliefs, the cat is a creature associated with demons, and even in beliefs

collected from Nakhchivan, it is said that the cat is a firishte. Firishte is also the offspring of a jinn. And since the offspring of a jinn is believed to be black, in mythological thinking, the black cat is also considered to be the offspring of a jinn. The next text of belief also clarifies this idea: “In any house or yard where there is a black cat, it is believed to be the offspring of a jinn. If a black cat crosses your path or appears in front of a car, it is believed that you will not have good luck. If you see it, stop the car. If you see it, stop (Examples of Sharur folklore. I book: 2016, 116).

However, in some examples, many of the concepts associated with the color black such as chicken, rooster, ram, and others – are presented as symbols of success.

Within the beliefs and trials of the region, in one of the hymns of the “Khidir Nabi” ceremony, the “chicken” associated with the color black is not the familiar chicken, but rather a bird known as the turdus (qaratoyuq). The blackbird is believed to symbolize good news. In this example, it is not a black chicken, but a turdus:

Xıdıra Xıdır deyəllər,
(Khidir must be called Khidir),
Xıdıra çörək verəllər.
(They give bread to Khidir).
Mən Xıdırın nəyiyəm?
(What am I to Khidir)?
Ayağının nalıyam,
(I am the horseshoe of his foot).
Xanım, ayağa dursana,
(Lady, stand up),
Yükün dalm açsana.
(Unpack your load).
Torbanı doldursana,
(Fill up the bag),
Qonağı yola salsana.
(Send the guest on their way).
Qara toyuğun qanadı,
(The wing of the **black** chicken),
Kim vurdu, kim sanadı?
(Who struck it, who counted it)?
Məhlənizə gələndə
(When we came to your neighborhood),
İtlər bizi taladı

(The dogs attacked us). (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. I: 2010, 87). There is also information that the concepts assigned by black color will bring good and success to events or people in these texts. The essence of the poetic example spoken by participants during the “papaq atma” (hat throwing) in the “Khidir Nabi” ceremony is a call to action for the fulfillment of the purpose “Xanım, ayağa dursana”. And in terms of hastening the fulfillment of the purpose, the issue of recalling the forbidden occurrence arises, where the color black is mentioned. “Qara toyuğun qanadı, Kim vurdu, kim sanadı?”. Therefore, the black color associated with the chicken is a symbol of success. It is meant to be protected and not disturbed.

Dam üstə qara toxlu, haxışta,
(On the roof, a **black** chicken, haxishta),
Arpanı yedi çoxlu, haxışta,
(Ate a lot of barley, haxishta),

Hamının yarı gəldi, haxışta,
(Everyone’s beloved arrived, haxishta),
Gəlmədi burnu poxlu, haxışta.
(Except for the snotty-nosed one, haxishta).

Qara toyuq hindədi, haxışta,
(The **black chicken** is in the henhouse, haxishta),
Yumurtası hindədi, haxışta,
(Its eggs are in the henhouse, haxishta),
Fatmanın şəkilləri, haxışta,
(Fatma’s pictures, haxishta),
Hasənin cibindədi, haxışta
(They are in Hasan’s pocket, haxishta).
(Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. II: 2011, 307).

In this example, the word **black** also expresses that the chicken is a symbol of success and abundance. The expression “black chicken” here combines wealth (barley), the desired good days (hamının yarı gəldi), as well as feelings of separation (gəlmədi...).

In the fourth verse, which is considered the decisive verse of the bayati,

Eləmi Qarabağı,
(Oh, Karabakh),
Gəncəni, Qarabağı.
(Oh, Ganja, Karabakh),
Bir cüt tərlan itirdim,
(I lost a pair of falcons),
Qoynunda qara bağı.

(The one with a black knot in its bosom)
(Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Anthology of Nakhchivan folklore. I: 2010, 352) – the color black is used in a determining function to express the main purpose. The “falcon with a black band, a black-striped ribbon on its side” is considered a symbol of success and joy-bringing bird. Here, the falcon takes on a metaphorical function. Naturally, the lost person in the work of the anonymous author could be either their son, brother, or someone else. In any case, a pair of brothers or sons are compared to the black-banded falcon, which adds a sense of sorrowful meaning to the bayati. In the epic tradition of our national oral art, the deep symbolism of colors is more noticeable. The moments related to the color black are more active in this position. The color black expresses absolute emptiness, just as it expresses absolute fullness in these examples. In the texts we cited as an example at the beginning, the black color meant absolute fullness. However, the phrases “black day”, “black luck”, and “black fate” that are actively used in our language indicate an inevitable void. In bayatis, which are among the best poetic examples of expressing human inner suffering, the expression “black day” is the most suitable means of expressing pain, suffering, and agony:

Gedirsən, yara deynə,
Təlini dara deynə.
Əgər mənə soruşsa,

Günümü qara deynə (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. Nakhchivan folklore. I: 1994, 274). As mentioned, we observe both positions of black in examples of epic tradition. In texts related to hearths, shrines, and sacred places, the color black definitely represents fullness and completeness. In other words,

the stone or wood, which is the main element of the shrine or hearth, signifies wholeness when defined by black. Here, black serves as a symbol of success and prosperity. In texts such as “Qara dash Shrine” and “Qara dash Shrine”, our ideas are confirmed. *“Black Stone Shrine. This shrine is associated with women. Men do not visit there. There is a black stone there. For pilgrimage. It is narrated that they placed it on the wall, and it slid off the wall and ended up in the middle of the house. She is a woman, she has disappeared. Whatever your intention is, you're going there”* (Examples of Sharur folklore. I book: 2016, 83); *“Qaraagac Srine. In that shrine, there was a tree, and it was said that they would take all the mad and ill people there. The tree itself was very black. People from the village said they could see the fire falling into the village at night. It was far away. No one went there. It is a very deep shrine”* (Examples of Sharur folklore. I book: 2016, 83). Here, it is believed that the stone and tree, designated by the color black, will bring success to a person. As mentioned, we observe both positions of black in examples of epic tradition. In other words, the functions of success, happiness, primacy, and wisdom associated with the black color, embedded in thoughts, have also sanctified the concepts designated by black, elevating them to the level of a shrine or hearth. The mythical thoughts in folk consciousness regarding the “movement” of the stone, the self-ignition and regeneration of the tree, stem from the functions of success, wisdom, and other qualities associated with black in ancient thoughts. In other words, this sanctity does not belong to the stone or the tree, but is directly related to the black color. And it is observed that black color also carries a protective function. In the texts above, we have presented descriptions of how the black-colored stone hearth or sanctuary has facilitated the creation of sacred places. Exactly from these beliefs, there are also ideas that black-colored small stones and black beads, when carried by people, possess protective functions. In the belief examples collected from Nakhchivan, it is mentioned that the black-colored stone called “baboul” or beads are used for protection against the evil eye and harm. According to some informants, baboul are stones brought as gifts by pilgrims during their pilgrimage to Mecca. This black stone has protective powers against evil spirits and the evil eye. In the ritual of cutting the hair of a newborn, the cloth spread under the child should be black in color, while performing the sacred act of cutting the hair at the age of forty (as discussed in the section on numbers, which holds sacred significance). The ritual of cutting the hair at forty marks the first phase of the newborn's transition into the cosmic world. In other words, the forty-day protection of the newborn (from the evil eye, bad influences, and so on) is considered essential according to folk beliefs. This period is celebrated because after forty days, baby enters the stage of having a body capable of fighting evil spirits. The use of the color black in the ritual of purification and cleansing after forty days is considered essential. In this context, black is regarded as a color that aids in the successful outcome of the purification ritual. At this time, a black-colored cloth is spread

under the child, and the purification water – the forty-day water – is poured onto that cloth, soaking into it. This, in turn, expresses the supportive and successful sacred position of the black color in the child's struggle against demonic forces during the forty-day period. The successful beginning formula of the black color is also clarified through the works of world literary figures such as Victor Hugo and Richard Wagner. According to their thinking, the dark opposite of black is the cosmic origin, and light symbolizes emerging from darkness, escaping from it, in contrast to clarity and purity. Jung noted that the carbon dioxide in the human body is black in color, whereas in diamonds, it is pure carbon and transparent like water. Diana Efess, considered the Earth Mother, is often depicted with hands and a face imagined in black, symbolizing her connection to the earth and the mysterious, protective qualities of the color black (Encyclopedia. Symbols, Signs, Emblems. Astrel: 2004, 259). During the research carried out on Nakhchivan folklore samples, it was found that black color carries the semantem of success within the samples. Although in modern times, the color black is associated with meanings of misfortune in phrases like “black day”, “black luck”, etc. Nevertheless, black has been regarded as a symbol of greatness, authority, knowledge, primacy, and even success since ancient times.

Conclusion: The article conducted an analysis of the deep sacramentality of white and black colors and their symbolism in folkloric examples. It is known that color holds a distinctive place in the system of signs that characterize objects. For modern man, a change in color does not harm the existence of an object. But for ancient man, an object had a natural, deeply sacramental world of its own color. Some of these symbolic expressions, which represent the meaning of various objects and events, carry traces of ancient cultures, while others have acquired new meanings, losing their original symbolism in the modern day. Some, on the other hand, have completely “forgotten” their symbolic function. It is imperative to admit that if today the color of the clothes we use in our daily life is important, then the symbolism of color goes far into the depths. Research conducted on folklore examples collected from the Nakhchivan region revealed that the deep symbolism of colors, considered to be primitive, such as white and black, is directly related to their deep sacramentality in ritualistic contexts. It is undeniable that women used white headscarves during funeral rituals in the past. Because this tradition still lives on to some extent. It is still observed that women in mourning houses in the village of Ganza, located in the Ordubad district of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, use white headscarves. However, this tradition is almost dying out in modern times, alongside the symbolism of success and victory that the color white has gained in expressions such as “white day” and “white luck”. And traces of this moment can be observed in the combination of the color white, which symbolizes defeat, with the “white flag”. The color white, which is used as a mourning color in the village of Ganza, and the white headscarf are also intended to express defeat and failure. However, despite all this, in

later periods, the symbolism of white as a color of happiness and success has cast a strong shadow over its original functions, which were associated with misfortune, defeat, and even mourning. Therefore, white color is chosen as a symbol of happiness and victory in accordance with the philosophy of color in the ancient Turkic world. We observe this in the performance of the yalli dance, which originated in the lands of Nakhchivan, in which the footman (the last participant in the yalli) dances with a white scarf in his hand. Here, the white scarf is perceived as a symbol of victory. During the research conducted on Nakhchivan folklore examples, it is obvious that the color black, despite the mourning and mourning character attributed to it in modern times, carries the semantics of success. In these examples, the color black is presented as a great, knowledgeable, pre-eminent, and primary symbol. In general, colors are a sign of symbolic interpretation in folk culture. The fact that they take on various meanings, taking place in examples of folk art, as well as in the facts of the ceremonial thought of the people, is a clear information about the thought of ancient culture.

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